

The Significance, Content and Functions of Teaching Mother Language and Reading Literacy Lessons in Primary Grades

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Annotation:

This article discusses the importance of mother tongue and reading literacy in primary schools. Important laws and regulations for improving students' literacy will be considered.

Keywords: mother tongue, reading literacy, science, importance, multimedia, video, animation, decoration.

The science of mother tongue and reading literacy is important in improving the oral and written literacy of primary school students. We know that today the content of mother tongue teaching in schools is the biggest stage in the development of our society and is adapted to the task set before the school by our state. Lessons taught in primary grades have a special place with their essence, goals and tasks. Because when the child comes to school, he does not yet know the rules of writing and expressing his speech. That is, students learn to write, speak, and express their thoughts these native language and reading literacy classes. In the process of learning mother tongue and reading literacy classes, students develop and work on skills that are common to many other educational subjects. As a result of teaching the mother tongue and reading, the students will be able to express their thoughts in a grammatically correct, clear sense, following the tone and write it correctly in terms of spelling. It was chosen to study the knowledge that will enable the conscious acquisition of the language in primary grades and the formation of graphic and spelling skills in students. In the section of phonetics and graphics, students acquire knowledge that will help them understand the

sound composition of words, the properties of vowels and consonants, the importance of sound in words in differentiating the meaning, including the connection between the sound and the graphic form is created mentally, i.e. consciously, and it is possible to write the word correctly. It serves as a program for the creation of a new generation of primary education textbooks and methodical manuals, as indicated in the newly revised "State Education Standards" for primary classes.

Primary school students learn word types: noun, adjective, number, pronoun, verb at different levels starting from the 1st grade. In grades 1-4, the study of all aspects of the language is taken into account, that is, elementary knowledge of phonetics, vocabulary, grammar and word formation is given in each grade. The educational process forms and develops the child's mental development, ability to think logically, worldview, literacy and self-awareness. It teaches us to be healthy in mind and spirit, to feel beauty and elegance, to love material existence, to internalize our traditions and to honor them by observing them and makes them better. In this regard, the implementation of such goals, which we set for primary education teachers, requires a clear definition of the content of education and a new approach to learning.

Literacy is the ability to perceive and practice the forms of written language that are required by society and valued by people. It is important for us to learn from the rich works of our ancestors and to teach them manners in order to raise primary school students to be high-spirited and mature individuals. In primary grades, a child's literacy is achieved through mother tongue and reading lessons. He learns to read and write. Not only have these subjects helped the student to master other subjects well. The main role in this will be focused on the teacher. The reason is that the professional skills and knowledge of the teacher play an important role in the literacy of primary school students.

First of all, to improve students' literacy, it is necessary to read correctly, pronounce correctly, increase vocabulary, develop speech, increase consciousness, thinking, and educate them into a well-rounded and healthy generation. In the development of the child's mind, it is very important that the transition from simple words to complex words is based on the state educational standards. Conducting mother tongue and reading literacy classes in information technology, like other subjects, helps to increase students' interest in classes and improve the quality of education. The use of multimedia tools has both educational and educational importance in increasing the effectiveness of classes. For example, the use of text, speech, music, decoration, pictures, video, animations and videos is achieved. In this way, it awakens the students' creative attitude in learning, increases their creativity, their ability to express themselves, increases their self-confidence, they can express their opinion about everything they learn. . Based on these aspects, it is necessary to say that every advanced modern teacher should be aware of the innovations in the education of the whole world, always be in search and be able to apply them in his work. Different tasks are used in the lessons.

The leading type of activity is search. These tasks have a higher level of difficulty than analytical tasks. The search task cannot be a template, it is always a new task aimed at studying the artistic texture of several, often two, texts, identifying the specific features of genres, the specific features of the artistic text with the result of work in the form ; conceptual table, cluster, test, sync or personal text. We have identified several types of search tasks. Note that this is the first time this methodology has been implemented.

The first type is to restore damaged texts, and then analyze them to determine the specific characteristics of text genres and types. As a result of the work, a conceptual table or cluster is created and your own text is created. For example, schoolchildren are offered to open prose and poetic texts on similar topics. To distinguish between two texts, students find signs of poetic and prose types of speech: the presence or absence of rhyme and rhythm, the presence of a narrator in one of the texts. In the process of this research, students feel the artistic texture of the work. In addition, it is suggested to write the poem separately and re-read the unopened texts in order not to

disturb the perception of the texts. To compare them, a conceptual table is filled, that is, at this stage we use technologies for developing critical thinking .

The second type of tasks is to compare the artistic text with a dictionary entry, with a picture, with another scientific or artistic text and acquire new knowledge on this basis. Solving these types of problems helps to better master the software material on the topic, develops skills for working with information presented in the form of text, graphic objects, and helps to develop speech.

The third type of tasks includes independent preparation of tests based on the texts of the works. It is difficult for the student to completely think out the test, he does not always pay attention to important questions. Therefore, we offer him test questions and he develops the answers himself, or we give him answer options, in which case the student's task is reduced to formulating the question. This task helps the student not only to improve his knowledge of science, but also to better understand the structure of the test (the student does not immediately understand that he needs to choose one wrong and one correct answer). After creating his test, the student exchanges notebooks with a friend and completes the task created by the friend, after which the correctness of the implementation and the correctness of the completed tasks are discussed.

There may seem to be a contradiction between the way we distinguish between task types and at the same time insist that a search task is always a new task. The contradiction is removed when describing each type of problem by providing different options for entering the terms of the problem (text + dictionary entry + graphic object; text + text + dictionary entry, etc.) and providing different options for presenting. Solution (table, text, etc.). The variety of combinations of different options allows us to call the proposed method of constructing search tasks a task constructor.

In conclusion, it should be said that every elementary school teacher should be able to diligently impart the necessary knowledge and skills to students with a deep understanding of mother tongue and reading literacy classes. Only then, in the future, students will grow up to be mature individuals with high written and oral literacy, fluent speech, and opinions.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. J.G. Yoldoshev, S. A. Usmanov. Fundamentals of pedagogical technology. "Teacher" 2004.
2. Mother tongue and reading literacy. Part 1 [Text]: textbook for 2nd grade K. Mavlanova. Republic Education Center, 2021.
3. The importance of using information technologies in mother tongue classes of primary education. Shukurova H.
4. Ahmedov S., Kasimov B., Kochkarov R., Rizayev Sh. Literature. Textbook for the 5th grade of general secondary schools. Part 2. - Tashkent: Sharq, 2015. - 176 p.
5. Ahmedov S., Kochogarov R., Rizayev Sh. Literature. Textbook-complex for the 6th grade of general secondary schools. Part 1. - Tashkent: Ma'naviyat, 2017. – 160.
6. Ahmedov S., Kochogarov R., Rizayev Sh. Literature. Textbook-complex for the 6th grade of general secondary schools. Part 2. - Tashkent: Ma'naviyat, 2017. – 160.
7. Ahmedov Q. Study of Hamza Hakimzoda's drama "Boy il Servant". - Tashkent: Teacher, 1968.
8. Aliev A. Studying the style of writing in school. - Tashkent: Teacher, 1974. – 88.
9. Boboev T. Poetry education. - Tashkent, Teacher, 1996.
10. "Boburnoma" miniatures / Editorial board: A. Qayumov, H. Sultonov, B. Alimov and others. - Tashkent: "Teacher" NMIU, 2008. - 240.